

Social Functioning in Schizophrenia and Bipolar Disorder Patients during COVID-19 PandemicSajal Sathiadevan¹, Deepak K S²¹Assistant Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Government Medical College, Palakkad, Kerala, India²Statistician, Department of Community Medicine, Government Medical College, Palakkad, Kerala, India

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Abstract:

During COVID pandemic studies have indicated social functioning is impaired in general population due to the perceived threat of COVID-19 and related lockdown measures. Studies have also suggested that patients with severe mental illness are disproportionately vulnerable to the COVID-19 pandemic effects on social functioning as compared to general population. Few studies have also suggested that social functioning in patients with severe mental illness was impaired prior to pandemic and there was no exacerbation in the social functioning deficits due to the pandemic. This study was done to assess the social functioning in patients with Schizophrenia and Bipolar disorder during the pandemic and to assess the relation between perceived threat due to COVID-19 and the social functioning in severe mental illness patients.

Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional assessment in 92 patients with severe mental illness comprising of Schizophrenia and Bipolar Disorder was conducted. Sociodemographic data and clinical data was collected using specifically designed proforma, Brief Psychiatric Rating scale, Young Mania Rating Scale, Hamilton Depression rating scale, Clinical global impression scale, Modified COVID-19 Threat scale and Work and Social Adjustment Scale were administered. Descriptive statistics were used to describe the data, Spearman's rank correlation was used to find correlation between WSAS and BPRS, YMRS, HAM-D, CGI and CTS and Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare WSAS and the sociodemographic variables.

Results: In this sample of 92 patients with severe mental illness 65 patients(70.7%) had significant social functioning impairment and 27 patients(29.3%) had good functioning during the pandemic. The mean WSAS score was 13.15±7.498. There was more functional impairment for male gender(15.08±6.42) as compared to female gender(11.67±5.976) and it was statistically significant (p=0.024) There was more functional impairment for Bipolar disorder patients(14.78±6.273) as compared to Schizophrenia patients (11.30± 6.416) and it was statistically significant (p=0.024). The CTS had a positive correlation with WSAS and was statistical significant (p<0.001) and suggest that COVID-19 related fear and anxiety was associated with significant functional impairment in patients with severe mental illness during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Conclusion: This study suggests that patients with severe mental illness had their social functioning affected during the pandemic and it was significantly more affected in males as compared to females, Bipolar disorder patients had more impairment in social functioning as compared to schizophrenia patients during the pandemic and social functioning deteriorates as COVID-19 related fear and anxiety increases.

Keywords: Social Functioning, Mental illness, COVID-19, Schizophrenia, Bipolar affective disorder.

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Introduction

Social functioning is impaired in patients with severe mental illness. [1,2] Schizophrenia and Bipolar affective disorder are considered as severe mental illness and is associated with significant disability.[3] Most studies have assessed disability in Schizophrenia and Bipolar disorder from a multidimensional perspective. Multiple dimensions of functioning like work, household activities, socialization are aspects considered by multiple scales to assess functioning in mental illness.[4,5] Patients with severe mental illness have impaired

social functioning regardless of pharmacological treatment. [6] Poor cognitive functions and negative symptoms lead to impaired psychosocial functioning in Schizophrenia and BPAD patients. [7,8,9,10] Although BPAD patients have episodic illness and during asymptomatic period are expected to have good social functioning, studies have shown significant social impairment in BPAD patients are similar to that of Schizophrenia patients.[11,12,13,14,15] The COVID-19 pandemic had significant impact on mental health of people

with severe mental illness and patients with severe mental illness are disproportionately vulnerable to psychological distress associated with COVID-19. [16,17] The psychological impact of COVID-19 pandemic had significant impairment in mental wellbeing of BPAD patients as compared to Schizophrenia patients. [18] Patients with severe mental illness had impaired social functioning during the pandemic compared to prepandemic functioning. [19] Individuals experiencing higher perceived vulnerability to COVID-19 have a negative impact on their mental health wellbeing. [20,21] This study was done to investigate the role of perceived threat to COVID-19 and its effects on the social functioning in Schizophrenia and Bipolar disorder patients

Materials and Methods

A cross-sectional hospital based study in 92 patients on follow up with severe mental illness comprising of Schizophrenia (F 20 ICD 10 criteria) and Bipolar Affective Disorder (F31 ICD 10 criteria) diagnosed as per ICD 10 criteria was conducted. [22] The patients for this study were recruited by convenient sampling and the study was conducted in Department of Psychiatry in District hospital Palakkad/Government Medical College Palakkad as outpatient or inpatient during COVID-19 pandemic between January to September 2021. The inclusion criteria for the participants were: minimum age of 18 years and above with a diagnosis of Schizophrenia or BPAD as per ICD-10 criteria registered in District Hospital Palakkad before October 2019 and on follow-up and willing for extensive clinical evaluation after obtaining written informed consent. An exclusion criteria was those not willing to take part in the study. Approval from Institutional Ethics Committee IEC/GMCPKD/31/20/85 dated 21/12/2020 was obtained prior to conducting the study.

Sample size was calculated based on the percentage of social functioning impairment in Schizophrenia patients of 80% observed in a study assessing social functioning in older Schizophrenia patients conducted in California. [23] Using the below equation with 95% confidence interval and 10 % precision the minimum required sample size was calculated as 90

$$n = \frac{4pq}{d^2} \text{ where } p = 80\%, q = 100 - p, d = \text{precision} = 10\% \text{ of } 80\%$$

Once the patients satisfied the inclusion criteria as assessed by the Psychiatrist and provided the written informed consent, sociodemographic details were collected using a specifically designed proforma for the study, clinical evaluation was done in all patients to assess the psychotic symptoms using BPRS scale, mood symptoms using YMRS and HAM-D scale, illness severity

using CGI scale, perceived threat due to COVID-19 using Modified COVID-19 Threat scale and functioning of the patient using Work and social Adjustment scale.

Tools: Sociodemographic Proforma to collect information related to age at assessment, gender, educational status, income, occupation, marital status, location, diagnosis, age at onset of illness, total duration of illness, total duration of treatment, total duration of follow-up at the current study centre. Modified Kuppaswamy rating scale was used to assess education and family income. [24]

Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale (BPRS)- It is a clinician rated scale to assess overall psychopathology. It is scale with 24 symptom constructs and the clinician rates each item on a 7 point scale which ranges from 1(not present) to 7 (extremely severe). [25]

Young Mania Rating Scale(YMRS). It is a clinician rated 11 item scale to measure mania symptoms. Each item is rated from 0 to 4 and higher scores suggests worsening of Mania symptoms. [26]

Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAM-D)- It is a clinician rated scale to assess depressive symptomatology. It is a 21 item scale with each item being rated 0 to 4 and higher scores suggests worsening of depressive symptoms over last 1 week. [27]

Clinical Global Impression – severity scale(CGI-S)- It is a clinician rated scale to assess severity of illness and is rated from 0 to 7 and higher scores suggest more severe illness. [28]

COVID-19 Threat scale(CTS)- It is a scale to measure the the degree of anxiety related to threat perception for COVID-19 pandemic. It is a 10 item scale and each item is rated on a likert scale from 1 to 5 with higher scores indicating higher anxiety. It was translated into Malayalam as per norms laid by World Health Organisation. [29,30]

Work and Social Adjustment Scale (WSAS)- It is a scale to assess the degree of functional impairment. Participants were provided instructions to rate how the COVID-19 Pandemic affected their various aspects of life in five domains(work, home management, social leisure, private leisure and close relationships). Participants rate it on a likert scale from 0 to 8 with higher score indicating greater functional impairment. The Malayalam translated version of this scale was used as per norms laid done by WHO for translation. [31,30]

Statistical Analysis: The data collected was entered in excel sheet and analysed by using IBM SPSS version 20. Frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation were calculated for categorical and continuous variables respectively. Spearman's rank correlation was used for finding the

correlation between WSAS and BPRS, YMRS, HAM-D, CGI, CTS. Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare the WSAS score between sociodemographic and clinical variables. P value less than 0.05 is taken as significance

Results

The study sample comprised of 92 patients with severe mental illness and comprised of 43 patients (46.74%) with a diagnosis of Schizophrenia and 49 patients (53.26%) with a diagnosis of Bipolar

affective disorder. The total sample of 92 patients with severe mental illness was analysed and subgroup analysis was not attempted. Demographic and clinical details of the sample is presented in Table 1. The mean age of the sample was 38.46 ± 13.35 years, with 52 patients (56.5%) of female gender, majority 41 patients (44.6%) having high school level of education, mostly of low economic status, unemployed (66.3%), majority from rural location 94.57% and 53.3% were married.

Table 1: Sociodemographic and Clinical characteristics of the sample

Characteristics	Total (n=92)	WSAS score BELOW 10 (n=27)	Significant functional impairment WSAS Score 10 and Above (n=65)
Age (years) (mean \pm SD)	38.46 \pm 13.35	40.85 \pm 15.22	37.48 \pm 12.50
Gender			
Male	40 (43.5%)	9	31
Female	52 (56.5%)	18	34
Education (%)			
Profession or Honours	2 (2.2%)	1	1
Graduate,	13 (14.1%)	5	8
Intermediate or Diploma,	18 (19.6%)	3	15
High school	41 (44.6%)	9	32
Middle school	12 (13%)	5	7
Primary school	4 (4.3%)	3	1
Illiterate	2 (2.2%)	1	1
Income			
>126360,	0	0	0
63182 to 126356,	0	0	0
47266 to 63178	3 (3.3%)	1 (33%)	2 (67%)
31591 to 47262,	1 (1.1%)	0	1 (100%)
18953 to 31589	11 (12%)	6 (54.5%)	5 (45.5%)
6327 to 18949	45 (48.9%)	7 (15.6%)	38 (84.4%)
<6323	32 (34.8%)	13 (40.6%)	19 (59.4%)
Occupation			
Employed	31 (33.7%)	9	22
Unemployed	61 (66.3%)	18	43
Marital status (%)			
Unmarried	33 (35.87%)	11	22
Married	49 (53.26%)	15	34
Divorced	9 (9.78%)	1	8
Widowed	1 (1.09%)	0	1
Location			
Rural	87 (94.6%)	27	60
Urban	5 (5.4%)	0	5
Diagnosis			
Schizophrenia	43 (46.7%)	16	27
BPAD	49 (53.3%)	11	38
Clinical Characteristics	Mean \pm SD	WSAS <10	WSAS 10 and above
Age at onset of illness in years	25.35 \pm 8.814	27.37 \pm 10.187	24.51 \pm 8.115
Total duration of illness in months	156.63 \pm 100.46	159.44 \pm 114.051	155.46 \pm 95.190
Total duration of treatment in months	134.63 \pm 100.99	140.78 \pm 117.667	132.08 \pm 94.110
Total duration of Follow-up in months	41.36 \pm 18.871	38.30 \pm 14.691	42.63 \pm 20.324
WSAS	13.15 \pm 7.498	5.67 \pm 3.026	16.26 \pm 4.865

The mean age of onset of illness was 25.35±8.814 years. With a mean duration of illness of 156.63±100.46 months (13 years).Majority of patients in the sample (62%) didn't have regular follow-up during COVID-19 pandemic but majority (78%) were able to continue their regular medicines during COVID-19 pandemic. 71.7% patients in this sample had their treatment monitored by a caregiver and majority of the caregiver 62 (67.4%) was of female gender. 37 % of patients in the

sample had symptom exacerbation prior to the pandemic and 37% of patients had exacerbation of illness during the pandemic.

The mean WSAS score was 13.15 ±6.54 with a median score of 13. The minimum score of WSAS was 0 and a maximum score was 29. In this sample 65 patients(70.7%) had a WSAS score of 10 and above suggesting a significant functional impairment and 27 patients (29.3%) had good functioning.

Table 2: Comparison between WSAS and Gender

Gender	N	Mean WSAS Score	SD	P-value
Male	40	15.08	6.814	0.024
Female	52	11.67	5.976	

Table 2 depicts the mean WSAS score for 40 male patients in this sample was 15.08±6.42 and for 52 female patients was 11.67±5.976 and was statistical significant (p=0.024) suggesting more functional impairment in male patients with severe mental illness in comparison to female gender.

Table 3: Comparison between WSAS and Diagnosis (Mann-Whitney- U Test)

Diagnosis	N	Mean WSAS Score	SD	P Value
Schizophrenia	43	11.30	6.416	0.024
BPAD	49	14.78	6.273	

Table 3 depicts the mean WSAS score for 43 patients with Schizophrenia was 11.30± 6.416 and for 49 BPAD patients was 14.78±6.273 and was statistical significant (p=0.024) suggesting BPAD patients had more functional impairment as

compared to Schizophrenia patients in this sample. The other sociodemographic and clinical variables didn't show a statistical significant difference in relation to WSAS score

Table 4: Correlation between WSAS and BPRS, YMRS,HAM-D, CGI-S, CTS

Correlation between WSAS and					
	BPRS	YMRS	HAM-D	CGI-S	CTS
Spearman rank correlation(r-value)	0.101	0.120	0.189	0.148	0.405
p-value	0.337	0.256	0.072	0.160	<0.001

Table 4 demonstrate that there was no statistical significant correlation between WSAS and BPRS, YMRS, HAM-D and CGI. Table 4 and Figure demonstrates that CTS had a positive correlation with WSAS and was statistical significant

(p<0.001) and suggest that COVID-19 related fear and anxiety was associated with significant functional impairment in patients with severe mental illness during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Figure 5: Correlation between work and social adjustment scale and COVID-19 threat scale

Discussion

This study was done to evaluate the functional impairment in severe mental illness during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study sample comprised of Schizophrenia and Bipolar disorder patients and had more of female gender (56.5%) and was predominantly from rural background (94.6%) and low economic status and majority having high school level of formal education and mostly unemployed. The patients in this study sample had nearly 13 years duration of severe mental illness and have been taking psychiatry treatment for nearly 11 years. The mean duration of followup in this treatment centre for these patients was 41 months.

Patients in this sample had WSAS mean score 13.15 suggesting mild to moderate level of social functioning impairment in Schizophrenia and Bipolar disorder patients during COVID-19 pandemic. In 70.7% patients of the sample had WSAS score of 10 and above suggesting social functioning was affected. In a 15 year follow-up study in patients with severe mental illness it was observed that social functioning impairment was present in nearly 64% of Schizophrenia. [32]

The social functioning impairment was significantly ($p=0.024$) more in males as compared to female gender in patients with severe mental illness in this study which is corroborated by other studies. Most studies have found better social functioning in women as compared to men. [33,34] In a study in subjects with high risk for psychosis found that men also had greater deficit in social functioning as compared to female gender. [35] In a study done in RML hospital, Delhi found male patients with Schizophrenia had better social function as compared to female gender. [36] A study conducted in Spain in Schizophrenia showed there is no gender difference observed in the social functioning in Schizophrenia patients. [37] A multi-centre study done in Europe also didn't find any gender difference in the social functioning in Schizophrenia patients. [38] In a study done in 1592 patients with a psychiatry diagnosis in Japan during initial phase of pandemic found that females had worsening of illness during pandemic than males. [39]

The social functioning in this sample was significantly ($p=0.024$) more impaired in Bipolar disorder patients as compared to Schizophrenia patients during this pandemic. Most studies suggest that social functioning is more impaired in Schizophrenia patients as compared to Bipolar disorder patients and Schizophrenia patients have more cognitive impairment and negative symptoms. [40] Previous studies have also indicated that Bipolar disorder even though has an episodic course, the social functioning even during

asymptomatic period is significantly affected and is comparable to functioning in Schizophrenia patients. [4,13,41] In a study done in Japan in 1592 patients with a Psychiatry diagnosis found Bipolar disorder patients had more worsening of illness during the pandemic as compared to Schizophrenia patients. [39] There might be higher expectation in caregivers regarding social functioning from BPAD patients than Schizophrenia during COVID-19 pandemic.

Social functioning in severe mental illness is affected by exacerbation of psychotic symptoms or mood symptoms and severity of illness, but this study couldn't demonstrate correlation between WSAS score and BPRS, YMRS, HAM-D and CGI severity score. In studies it has shown that cognitive symptoms and negative symptoms were correlated with social functioning rather than psychotic symptoms. [42] In a systematic review it was observed that social cognition influences functioning in Schizophrenia more than neurocognitive abilities. [43] An epidemiological study in 1983 suggested that symptoms in severe mental illness were not correlated with social functioning in the community sample. [44] In a study with a small sample size of 25 patients mostly in remission phase of Schizophrenia done in Mumbai couldn't find an association with symptomatology in Schizophrenia patients and functioning. [45]

There was a positive correlation between CTS score and WSAS suggesting that an increase in COVID-19 related fear leads to deterioration in the social functioning in patients with severe mental illness. A study of influence of COVID-19 threat on subjective well-being indicates that as patient's perceived COVID-19 threat increase there is a detrimental effect on subjective mental well-being of patients. [20] A study conducted in Spain during the initial period of COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 suggested that Bipolar Disorder and Schizophrenia patients were lesser affected in their global functioning during lockdown as compared to Anxiety and Depression patients. Bipolar Disorder and Schizophrenia patients were not working, had restricted social network and were mostly spending time at home even prior to pandemic and hence didn't experience much deterioration in global functioning as compared to Depression and anxiety disorder patients. [46]

Limitations: The study had a smaller sample and was a cross-sectional design with only one point of assessment and didn't have a baseline assessment of functioning prior to COVID-19.

Conclusion

This study suggests that patients with severe mental illness had their social functioning affected during the pandemic and it was significantly more affected

in males as compared to females, Bipolar disorder patients had more impairment in social functioning as compared to schizophrenia patients during the pandemic and social functioning deteriorates as COVID-19 related fear and anxiety increases.

Ethics Approval and Consent to Participate in Study: Ethics Committee IEC/GMCPKD/31/20/85 dated 21/12/2020 was obtained prior to conducting the study. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to participating in the study.

List of Abbreviations:

BPAD- Bipolar affective disorder, COVID-19-Corona virus-19, WSAS- Work and social adjustment scale, CTS- COVID Threat Scale, BPRS- Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale, YMRS- Young Mania Rating scale, HAM-D- Hamilton Depression rating Scale, CGI-S- Clinical Global Impression- Severity scale.

Data Availability: Data available with corresponding author.

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Authors Contribution: 1st author was involved in research design, collecting data, compiling data and writing the article, 2nd author was involved in statistical analysis and writing the article.

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